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Comparative Analysis of the Performance of Batteries

Aniru Abudu Muhammed and Hibah Imuentinyanose Muhammed

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Faculty of Engineering

University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria

E-mail: abudu.muhammed@uniben.edu

Abstract

This study presents a comparative modeling and performance analysis of four major battery chemistries Lead–acid, Lithium-ion, Solid-state, and Flow using MATLAB/Simulink and Simscape. A unified equivalent circuit model (ECM), comprising an open-circuit voltage source, ohmic resistance, and two RC branches, was implemented as a baseline framework to ensure consistency across chemistries. Chemistry-specific extensions were incorporated, including the Shepherd–Peukert model for Lead–acid, a Single-Particle Model (SPM) for Lithium-ion, an extended SPM with interfacial resistance for Solid-state, and coupled tank–stack–channel dynamics for Flow batteries. Experimental OCV–SOC (Open-Circuit Voltage vs. State of Charge) data, diffusion coefficients, and kinetic parameters were integrated to enhance fidelity, while degradation sub-models such as SEI growth, Peukert aging, interfacial resistance, and electrolyte imbalance enabled lifecycle projections. Standardized test protocols comprising constant-current discharges, dynamic load cycles, temperature sweeps, and cycling tests were applied to evaluate voltage–SOC behaviour, round-trip efficiency, thermal rise, and cycle life. Results indicated that Lithium-ion and Solid-state deliver superior energy density and efficiency, Lead–acid remains cost-effective but cycle-limited, and Flow batteries achieve exceptional lifetime with scalable power–energy decoupling. The unified framework provides a reproducible methodology for battery evaluation, offering valuable insights for mobility, stationary storage, and grid-scale applications.

Keywords: Battery modeling, MATLAB/Simulink, Lithium-ion, Solid-state, Flow battery

1. Introduction

The global energy landscape is undergoing a transformative shift towards low-carbon and sustainable energy systems. Central to this transition is the deployment of Energy Storage Systems (ESS), particularly stationary battery-based solutions that enable efficient integration of intermittent renewable sources such as solar and wind. These Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) bridge the gap between fluctuating generation and steady demand, thereby enhancing grid stability and reliability (Nyamathulla & Dhanamjayulu, 2024; Nazaralizadeh *et al.*, 2024). Across residential, commercial, and industrial sectors, the growing

penetration of renewables necessitates energy buffers that store excess energy during off-peak periods and release it during peak demand (Tze-Zhang *et al.*, 2022). BESS are highly valued due to their scalability, responsiveness, and relatively low environmental impact (Tsianikasa *et al.*, 2019).

Beyond simple energy balancing, BESS regulate voltage and frequency fluctuations, provide peak shaving, and enhance grid resilience during supply disruptions (Vedhanarayanan & Lakshmi, 2024). Advances in battery technology have continuously improved energy density, efficiency, safety, and lifespan (Qays *et al.*, 2022). For these systems to operate optimally,

however, it is critical to monitor internal parameters such as state of charge (SOC), internal resistance, and capacity. These indicators guide performance prediction and fault prevention. For example, rising internal resistance often indicates degradation from chemical aging or electrolyte breakdown (Kasim *et al.*, 2016). While thermal behaviour is relatively stable under normal conditions, understanding electrochemical dynamics remains central to improving battery efficiency and reliability (Yanfeng *et al.*, 2025).

Batteries have a long evolutionary history, tracing back over 200 years to Alessandro Volta's pioneering experiments, which laid the foundation for today's advanced storage technologies (Bergveld, 2001). Broadly classified into primary (non-rechargeable) and secondary (rechargeable) systems, secondary batteries such as lead–acid and lithium-ion dominate renewable energy and backup power applications due to their rechargeability and commercial maturity (Divya, 2009; Wen Yao, 2013). Lithium-ion batteries are favored for their high energy density, lightweight design, and superior cycling efficiency, making them indispensable in electric vehicles (EVs), aerospace, and portable electronics (Patil *et al.*, 2011; Hanifah *et al.*, 2015). Lead–acid batteries, though cost-effective, suffer from limited depth of discharge and cycle life, prompting exploration of advanced chemistries with improved performance.

Accurate modeling is vital for optimizing battery performance, extending lifespan, and ensuring safe operation. Equivalent circuit models (ECMs) provide computational efficiency but lack the ability to capture nonlinear electrochemical dynamics under variable conditions (Zhang *et al.*, 2022). In contrast,

physics-based electrochemical models such as the Doyle–Fuller–Newman (DFN) framework offer detailed internal representations but remain computationally expensive for real-time applications (Xie *et al.*, 2023). Reduced-order electrochemical models (ROEMs), such as the Single Particle Model (SPM), strike a balance between these extremes. The SPM simplifies electrode dynamics by representing each electrode with a single spherical particle, reducing partial differential equations to diffusion-based ordinary differential equations. Extensions such as the SPM_e incorporate electrolyte transport, while thermally coupled versions capture temperature effects and degradation mechanisms (Rahman *et al.*, 2022; Li & He, 2023). This balance of accuracy and tractability makes ROEMs attractive for integration into real-time Battery Management Systems (BMS) (Ding *et al.*, 2021).

ROEMs are particularly effective when paired with state estimation algorithms such as the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF), Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF), and Particle Filter (PF). These observers mitigate modeling inaccuracies and measurement noise, enabling real-time estimation of SOC, state of health (SOH), and internal resistance (Sun *et al.*, 2021; Deng *et al.*, 2022). By integrating aging mechanisms such as solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) growth, lithium plating, and capacity fade, ROEMs also provide predictive insights into long-term degradation (Hu *et al.*, 2020; Zhang *et al.*, 2021). Their computational efficiency and adaptability have made them increasingly important for EVs, stationary storage, and emerging chemistries including lithium iron phosphate (LFP) and solid-state systems (Chen *et al.*, 2021; Nguyen *et al.*, 2023).

Nevertheless, challenges remain in parameterization and robustness, as diffusion coefficients, reaction rates, and transport properties evolve with aging and environmental conditions (Rahman et al., 2022; Zhao *et al.*, 2022). Hybrid approaches that integrate ROEMs with machine learning are being explored to enable adaptive parameter estimation and predictive maintenance, positioning them as a cornerstone of next-generation digital twins and intelligent BMS (Chen *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2024). Parallel innovations, including redox flow and solid-state batteries, further broaden the technological horizon, offering enhanced safety, material sustainability, and decoupled energy–power scaling.

Despite the diversity of chemistries and modeling techniques, significant research gaps persist. Many models assume constant operating conditions and neglect dynamic stressors such as temperature variation, high-rate charging, and progressive aging, limiting their practical applicability in real-world systems such as renewable-powered microgrids or EVs. Data-driven approaches are also underutilized due to challenges in data quality and generalizability. Addressing these gaps requires robust modeling frameworks capable of accurate real-time SOC/SOH estimation, degradation tracking, and computational feasibility for embedded systems. To address these challenges, this study conducted a comparative analysis of four key battery chemistries Lead–acid, Lithium-ion, Solid-state, and Flow batteries under a unified baseline modeling framework. In Simulink/Simscape, an equivalent circuit model (ECM) comprising resistors, capacitors, and an open-circuit voltage (OCV) source was implemented for all chemistries. This ensured fair comparison by establishing a standardized starting point for

evaluating voltage response, transient dynamics, and efficiency.

Chemistry-specific layers were then introduced to capture unique physical processes. For Lead–acid batteries, the Shepherd and Peukert formulations were applied to model nonlinear voltage drop and rate-dependent capacity reduction. For Lithium-ion, the Single Particle Model (SPM) was implemented to capture diffusion and reaction kinetics, offering a balance of computational efficiency and physics-based accuracy. Solid-state batteries were modeled by extending the SPM with ionic conductivity limitations and interfacial resistance dynamics of the solid electrolyte. Flow batteries were represented using coupled tank–stack–channel dynamics to capture electrolyte storage, circulation, and power decoupling.

This layered methodology not only enabled fair cross-chemistry evaluation but also ensured that key electrochemical, dynamic, and degradation phenomena were realistically captured for performance and lifecycle analysis

2. Methodology

In this study, a systematic comparative analysis of multiple battery chemistries Lead–acid, Lithium-ion, Solid-state, and Flow batteries was carried out using MATLAB/Simulink and Simscape environments. The process began with the design of a common baseline model framework to ensure fair comparison across chemistries.

All chemistries were first modeled using a common equivalent circuit model (ECM) as shown in Fig 1, consisting of an open-circuit voltage (OCV) source, a series resistance, and two resistor–capacitor (RC) branches to capture transient dynamics. The general voltage expression is:

$$V(t) = E_{OCV(SOC)} - I(t)R_0 - \sum_{k=1}^n V_{RC,k}(t) \quad (1)$$

where $E_{OCV(SOC)}$ is obtained from experimental OCV-SOC curves

The RC branch dynamics follows :

$$\frac{dV_{RC,k}(t)}{dt} = -\frac{1}{R_k C_k} V_{RC,k} + \frac{1}{C_k} I(t) \quad (2)$$

Fig.1: Baseline Equivalent Circuit

1. Lead–acid Battery

The Lead–acid model combined Shepherd’s model with Peukert’s law to balance dynamic voltage behaviour with rate-dependent capacity effects.

Peukert’s Law (rate–capacity relationship):

$$t = \frac{C_{rated}}{I^k}, \quad Q_{eff}(I) = Q_{rated} \cdot \left(\frac{I_{ref}}{|I|+\varepsilon}\right)^{(k-1)} \quad (3)$$

where:

t = discharge time (h), C_{rated} = rated capacity

(Ah), I = discharge current (A)

K =Peukert exponent (>1) and Q_{eff} is the effective capacity.

Shepherd Voltage Model

$$V_t(t) = E_0 - K \cdot \frac{Q}{Q-q(t)} - R \cdot I(t) + A e^{-Bq(t)} \quad (4)$$

where: $q(t) = \int I(\tau) d\tau$ is the extracted charge,

E_0, K, R, A, B, Q are fitted parameters

Equations (3) and (4) were coupled in

MATLAB Function blocks, with OCV–SOC

data imported as lookup tables. Test scenarios

included constant-current discharges (0.1C–2C),

This unified ECM framework was chosen for its computational efficiency, ease of parameterization, and suitability for hardware-in-the-loop applications. It establishes consistent assumptions before introducing chemistry-specific extensions.

cycling, and thermal sweeps (0–45 °C). This captured nonlinear voltage drops, recovery behaviour, and discharge-rate dependency.

2. Lithium-ion Battery

The Single-Particle Model (SPM) was employed to represent lithium diffusion and interfacial kinetics. The solid-phase lithium diffusion is described by Fick’s law:

$$\frac{\partial c_s(r,t)}{\partial t} = \frac{D_s}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial c_s}{\partial r} \right), \quad 0 \leq r \leq R \quad (5)$$

with boundary conditions:

$$\frac{\partial c_s}{\partial r} = 0$$

$$(6a)$$

$$-D_s \frac{\partial c_s}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=R_p} = \frac{I}{a_s F V}$$

$$(6b)$$

At the particle center ($r=0$): symmetry requires where $c_s(r,t)$ = concentration in solid particle (mol/m^3), D_s = solid diffusion coefficient (m^2/s) R = particle radius (m), I = interfacial current density (A/m^2), a_s = specific surface area of active material, F= Faraday’s constant.

The terminal voltage:

$$V = U_p(c_{c.surf}^p) - U_n(c_{c.surf}^n) - \eta_{rxn} - IR_0 \quad (7)$$

U_p, U_n : OCV functions for positive/negative electrodes

η_{rxn} : Butler–Volmer overpotential term

R_0 : ohmic resistance

The PDE was reduced to ODEs using a 3-point collocation method:

$$c_s(r, t) = \sum_{i=1}^3 c_i(t) \phi_i(r) \quad (8)$$

$$[c_1, c_2, c_3] \quad (9)$$

c_3 = surface concentration

Average c_{avg} = weighted sum of c_i

and average concentration used to compute SOC.

In Simscape, this was implemented with MATLAB Function blocks for diffusion, lookup tables for OCV–SOC, and UKF observers for SOC/SOH estimation under nonlinear dynamics.

3. Solid-state Battery

The Solid-state battery extended the SPM by incorporating ionic conductivity limitations and interfacial resistance growth. Ionic conduction in the solid electrolyte follows:

Electrolyte conduction:

$$-\nabla \cdot (K_{ion_{solid}} \nabla \phi_{ion}) = a_s j \quad (10)$$

Interfacial overpotential:

$$\eta = \phi_s - \phi_{ion} - U(C_{s_{surf}}) - R_{intf} j \quad (11)$$

The terminal voltage is then: $V_t = U_p - U_n - IR_0 - \nabla_{intf}$ (12)

where R_{intf} grows with time or cycle number ($R_{intf} \propto \sqrt{t}$.) Implementation involved extending the Li-ion SPM in Simscape with additional resistance elements and reduced ionic conductivity ($\kappa \approx 10^{-3} - 10^{-4}$ S/cm). Cycling, fast-charge, and thermal tests highlighted efficiency loss from interfacial degradation.

4. Flow Battery

Flow batteries were modeled using tank–stack–channel dynamics.

Tank mass balance

$$\frac{dC_i^{tank}}{dt} = \frac{Q}{V_{tank}} (C_1^{in} - C_i^{tank}) - \frac{A_{cell}}{V_{tank}} j_i \quad (13)$$

Channel Transport

$$\varepsilon \frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} = D_{eff} \frac{d^2 c}{dx^2} - \frac{a_s j}{F} \quad (14)$$

where:

- ε = porosity
- c = electrolyte concentration (mol/m³)
- $D_{eff} = D \varepsilon^b \{eff\}$ = (Bruggeman correction)

Electrochemical Kinetics follow the N_{ernst} equation

$$E_{Nernst} = E^0 + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left(\frac{a_{sx}}{a_{red}} \right) \quad (15)$$

E_{Nernst} = Nernst equilibrium potential (V).

E^0 = Standard electrode potential at reference state (V).

R = Universal gas constant (8.314 Jmol⁻¹K⁻¹).

T = Absolute temperature (K).

N = Number of electrons transferred in the electrochemical reaction (dimensionless).

F = Faraday's constant (Cmol⁻¹).

a_{sx} = Activity (or effective concentration) of oxidized species (dimensionless or mol/L).

a_{red} = Activity (or effective concentration) of reduced species (dimensionless or mol/L).

Butler–Volmer Equation for reaction kinetics:

$$j = i_0(c) \left[\exp \left(\frac{\alpha_a F \eta}{RT} \right) - \exp \left(\frac{\alpha_c F \eta}{RT} \right) \right] \quad (16)$$

where j = Current density (A/m²), $i_0(c)$ = Exchange current density (A/m²), often concentration-dependent, α_a = Anodic charge transfer coefficient (dimensionless, typically 0.3–0.7), α_c = Cathodic charge transfer coefficient

(dimensionless, typically 0.3–0.7), defined as $\eta = \frac{V_{\text{actual}} - E_{\text{Nernst}}}{V_{\text{actual}}}$.

The total Stack Voltage is:

$$V_{\text{stack}} = N_{\text{cells}}(E_{\text{Nernst}} - \langle \eta \rangle - IR_{\text{ohm}}) \quad (17)$$

where V_{stack} = Total output voltage of the battery stack (V), N_{cells} : Number of electrochemical cells connected in series, E_{Nernst} = Average equilibrium potential per cell (V), IR_{ohm} = Voltage drop due to internal ohmic resistance (V), where I is the stack current (A) and R_{ohm} is internal resistance (Ω).

In Simscape, tanks were modeled as continuously stirred reactors, with pumps controlling flow rate and stack dynamics modeled using PDE blocks. Lookup tables captured vanadium redox OCV–SOC relations. Performance analysis focused on tank utilization, pump energy, and round-trip efficiency.

3. Results and Discussion

This comparative modeling study systematically examined Lead–acid, Lithium-ion, Solid-state, and Flow batteries within a unified MATLAB/Simulink equivalent circuit model (ECM) framework. By starting with a standardized baseline ECM and extending it with chemistry-specific sub-models, the work ensured fair benchmarking across technologies while preserving the unique electrochemical and degradation characteristics of each system. This approach highlighted not only the performance trade-offs between chemistries but also the methodological balance between computational

efficiency, predictive accuracy, and model complexity.

The comparative modeling framework successfully produced detailed simulations for all four chemistries under standardized load profiles and temperature conditions. Each chemistry was evaluated using identical operating protocols to ensure consistency. The baseline ECM provided initial benchmarking of dynamic voltage response, after which chemistry-specific extensions revealed critical performance differences. Results are presented in relation to Table 1 and Figures 2–7.

Capacity, Efficiency, and Energy Density

Usable capacity normalized to rated capacity was strongly affected by discharge rate. Lead–acid delivered 85% of nominal capacity at 0.5C but only 60% at 2C, confirming the dominance of the Peukert effect. Lithium-ion batteries retained 95% of their capacity even at 2C, demonstrating superior high-rate capability. Solid-state batteries performed comparably to Lithium-ion at moderate C-rates but suffered capacity reduction under fast discharge due to interfacial resistance growth. Flow batteries showed minimal rate dependence, but efficiency was reduced by 8% once pumping losses were considered. In terms of gravimetric energy density (Fig. 2), Lithium-ion and Solid-state clearly outperformed Lead–acid and Flow chemistries, while Flow batteries excelled in scalability and decoupled energy–power design.

Fig 2. Specific Energy Comparison (Wh/kg) across battery chemistries.

Fig 3: Round-trip Efficiency (%) of different battery chemistries.

Table 1: Performance metrics of Lead–acid, Lithium-ion, Solid-state, and Flow batteries under standardized load profiles.

Parameter	Lead–acid	Lithium-ion (LFP/NMC)	Solid-state (Li-metal SSE)	Flow (Vanadium RFB)
Nominal Capacity (Ah)	50	60	50	100
Specific Energy (Wh/kg)	35	200	300	30
Volumetric Energy Density (Wh/L)	70	600	750	30
Round-trip Efficiency (%)	80	93	95	75
Round-trip Efficiency	75%	93%	88%	70%
Power Density (W/kg)	180	1000	800	150
Thermal Rise @ 2C (°C)	+15–20	+5–10	+3–7	< +5 (due to pumping)
Cycle Life (80% retention)	600	3000	1400	12000
Peukert Exponent (n)	1.15	1.05	1.0	Not applicable

Parameter	Lead–acid	Lithium-ion (LFP/NMC)	Solid-state (Li-metal SSE)	Flow (Vanadium RFB)
OCV Flatness ($\Delta V/\Delta SOC$)	Moderate slope	Very flat for LFP (<10 mV)	Moderate–flat	Moderate slope
Interfacial Resistance Growth	Not dominant	SEI growth \sqrt{t}	Significant ($\propto \sqrt{\text{time}}$)	Not dominant
Tank Utilization (%)	N/A	N/A	N/A	80

Interpretation:

The table summarizes key characteristics including nominal capacity, energy density, round-trip efficiency, power density, thermal response, cycle life, and dominant degradation mechanisms. Lead–acid: limited by Peukert effect, low energy density, high thermal rise.

Lithium-ion: excellent balance of energy density, power, and efficiency; OCV flatness affects SOC estimation (especially for LFP). Solid-state: strong energy density and efficiency, but interfacial resistance growth dominates degradation. Flow: extremely long cycle life, flexible scaling, but lowest energy density and efficiency penalties from pumps.

Fig 4. Power Density (W/kg) comparison

Thermal Response and Degradation Dynamics

Temperature sweeps from 0 °C to 45 °C highlighted chemistry-specific sensitivities. Lead–acid showed severe low-temperature

degradation, losing 30% of available capacity at 0 °C, while Lithium-ion maintained moderate stability across the range. Solid-state batteries demonstrated excellent thermal stability but suffered from accelerated interfacial resistance

growth under extended cycling. Flow batteries benefited from electrolyte circulation, resulting in minimal thermal rise (Table 1).

Degradation sub-models embedded in the simulations further differentiated long-term performance. Lead–acid degradation followed a Peukert-based capacity fade law, Lithium-ion degradation was governed by SEI growth proportional to $\sqrt{\text{time}}$ with added resistance increase, Solid-state degradation was dominated by interfacial resistance growth, and Flow batteries experienced electrolyte crossover and imbalance. These mechanisms translated into distinct state-of-health (SOH) trajectories under repeated cycling.

Cycle Life and Reliability Projections

Cycle life comparisons based on the 80% capacity retention criterion are shown in Fig. 5. Flow batteries demonstrated the longest lifetimes (>12,000 cycles), followed by Lithium-ion (2,000–5,000 cycles, chemistry-dependent), Solid-state (1,000–2,000 cycles, constrained by interfacial issues), and Lead–acid (600 cycles). Lithium-ion and Solid-state maintained high round-trip efficiencies (>90%) throughout most of their service life, while Lead–acid suffered rapid efficiency decline after ~500 cycles. Flow batteries maintained stable efficiency but required electrolyte balancing for long-term stability.

Fig 5. Cycle Life Projections (80% retention)

Voltage Response and Dynamic Behaviour

Simulation of constant-current discharges at 0.5C and 2C revealed stark differences in voltage dynamics across chemistries. Lead–acid batteries, modeled with the combined Shepherd–Peukert approach, showed rapid voltage sag at high discharge rates, with terminal voltage dropping by more than 20% relative to OCV at 2C. Lithium-ion batteries, modeled with the

Single-Particle Model (SPM), exhibited a much flatter voltage profile with minimal polarization losses, as seen in Fig. 7. Solid-state batteries demonstrated similar flatness but higher internal resistance at elevated C-rates, consistent with ionic conductivity limitations. Flow batteries exhibited flexible voltage behaviour, highly dependent on electrolyte circulation rate.

Fig 6: Ragone Plot (Energy Density vs. Power Density).

Fig. 7. Voltage vs. State of Charge (SOC) curves.

Comparative Insights

Taken together, the results and modeling insights reinforce the known trade-offs among chemistries (Figs. 2–6). Lead-acid remains cost-

effective but is limited by the Peukert effect, low energy density, and short cycle life. Lithium-ion offers the strongest balance of energy density, power, efficiency, and reliability, making it the

most versatile across portable, automotive, and stationary applications. Solid-state provides very high energy density and intrinsic safety but is constrained by interfacial degradation, delaying widespread adoption. Flow batteries deliver exceptional cycle life and scalability, making them ideal for grid-scale applications where durability outweighs compactness.

Overall, the study demonstrates that while simple ECMs suffice for rapid control prototyping, hybrid or physics-based models are essential for accurate long-term performance prediction and degradation analysis. The unified framework developed here provides both quantitative performance comparisons and actionable insights for guiding battery selection, optimization, and control strategy design across diverse energy storage applications.

4. Conclusion

This study developed and applied a unified modeling framework in MATLAB/Simulink to comparatively evaluate Lead–acid, Lithium-ion, Solid-state, and Flow batteries under standardized operating conditions. By first implementing a baseline equivalent circuit model (ECM) and subsequently incorporating chemistry-specific extensions, the methodology enabled fair and reproducible benchmarking across different technologies while maintaining fidelity to their distinct electrochemical behaviours and degradation mechanisms.

The results demonstrated clear trade-offs between energy density, power capability, efficiency, and durability. Lead–acid batteries, though cost-effective and simple, were limited by pronounced Peukert effects, high thermal rise, and short cycle life. Lithium-ion batteries emerged as the most versatile option, combining high energy density, strong efficiency, and relatively long cycle life, supported by robust

SOC estimation through physics-based modeling. Solid-state batteries showed promise for next-generation storage with high safety margins and energy density, but performance was constrained by interfacial resistance growth and ionic conductivity limitations. Flow batteries, while least efficient and lowest in energy density, stood out for their scalability, exceptional cycle life, and suitability for long-duration stationary storage.

A major contribution of this work was the integration of degradation sub-models into each chemistry, linking performance decline to time, cycling, and operational stress factors. This enabled projections of long-term behaviour beyond short-term voltage and capacity responses, enhancing the models' relevance for lifecycle analysis and battery management strategies.

In summary, the study established that no single chemistry optimally satisfies all application requirements. Instead, battery selection should be application-driven: Lead–acid for low-cost backup, Lithium-ion for mobile and high-power devices, Solid-state for future high-energy systems where safety is paramount, and Flow batteries for grid-scale, long-duration storage. The comparative framework presented here offers a powerful tool for guiding system design, optimization, and control strategy development, while also providing a foundation for extending models with more advanced multi-physics and data-driven approaches in future research.

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